

Marketing Communication Strategy in Efforts to Strengthen Local UMKM Products

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Strategy, Communication, Marketing, Strengthening, Local Products

Received : 20, August

Revised : 23, September

Accepted: 30, October

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ABSTRACT

UMKM in Indonesia have experienced a significant increase, including in Banggai Laut Regency, where UMKM are starting to develop and become famous at the global level. Apart from the enthusiasm and support of the government, this cannot be separated from marketing efforts. In this article, the author presents a marketing strategy that aims to improve local UMKM products so that they are able to penetrate and maintain the national market. Apart from the enthusiasm and support of the government, this cannot be separated from marketing efforts. The aim of this study is none other than to provide strategic material so that UMKM products can be successful in the domestic and national markets. The implementation method is carried out by preparing the program through mentoring on regular innovation strategies based on market needs, strategies for creating market demand, market expectations, formulating a pricing strategy that suits the market, flexibility, and socio-economic considerations of consumers. This analysis was carried out using a qualitative descriptive approach. It is hoped that local products made by UMKM, especially in Banggai Laut district, can gain recognition in local and national markets through the implementation of these strategies

INTRODUCTION

Banggai Laut Regency, which has abundant marine resources, history, and culture, is trying to empower and develop MSMEs. Natural wealth can be converted into profitable products. If activists and creative communities have the ability and sensitivity to manage the resources in the environment around them, it will be an extraordinary business opportunity, especially if not many people have yet to do so. There are many micro and small businesses in Banggai Laut, one of the districts in Central Sulawesi Province. It is truly extraordinary when local governments are able to encourage local communities to participate in the management and utilization of regional economic potential. So that UMKM scale products can develop and become successful in large industries, the role of government and community leaders is very important. UMKM products can increase economic capacity, improve the welfare of local communities, and increase income in various local sectors. It is hoped that existing UMKM can generate profits from managing natural resources in Banggai Laut Regency. However, unfortunately, many of them chose to go out of business because of difficulties in penetrating the market.(Yoyon Mudjiono, 2015).

Marketing communications, according to De Lozier, is the process of delivering and combining stimuli to the target market with the aim of increasing response and interest in the product. The goal of marketing communications is to establish channels for receiving, interpreting, and acting on market messages with the aim of adapting the company's current concept and finding new opportunities for communication. In the marketing process, communication is very important, and marketing success depends on communication. Even in the 1990s, marketing and communications were one, and communications became an important part of the marketing mix. (Alifahmi, 2005).

Marketing is the main issue in the development of UMKM in Banggai Laut Regency, and if the marketing strategy is not well prepared and not executed professionally, there is no guarantee that it will penetrate the market in the best way. The product quality is good and the packaging is good, but without the right marketing strategy, it will not be able to enter the market, especially in the highly competitive national market, which also faces many challenges. To produce effective marketing communications, a new approach is needed. One way is to carry out marketing communications. Marketing communications are activities that combine advertising with other marketing communications such as public relations, direct marketing, sales promotions, and sponsorship to work together. (Philip Kotler, 2001). According to Prisgunanto (2006:8) Marketing communication is part of marketing, which includes communication between the company and the target audience in various forms with the aim of improving marketing performance.

Meanwhile, according to (Dharmmesta, Basu Swastha and Handoko, 2012) Marketing communication is a type of communication carried out by buyers and sellers and is a process that helps in making marketing decisions and directs exchanges in a better direction by providing better information for

each party. By using appropriate marketing communication strategies, UMKM products in Banggai Laut Regency can be strengthened so that they are able to penetrate local and national markets optimally. This article discusses how marketing communication strategies can strengthen UMKM products so that they can penetrate local and national markets optimally.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This article is to be able to answer the current challenges of what is the right strategy to help UMKM penetrate local and national markets in marketing communications studies.

METHODOLOGY

Time and place of implementation of activities

We chose the activity location at the house of the head of the UMKM in Lampa Village, Banggai District, Banggai Laut Regency. Activities will take place from Agustus to September 2023. In this article, the qualitative case study method used is a type of contextual research that uses humans as subjects and is adapted to situations that are suitable for collecting qualitative data. According to (Bogdan, 1992) (Lexy. J. Moleong, 2000) is a research process that produces descriptive data that includes the behavior and written or spoken words of the research subject.

Primary and secondary data are collected through grouping. Because this research method is qualitative, the data collection methods used include observation (or observations), indepth interviews, and documentation. Data analysis is an effort to systematically find and organize notes from observations, interviews, and documentation to increase the researcher's understanding based on the problem being studied.

The implementation stage began with observations of the community and Lampa village officials, Banggai Subdistrict, and Banggai Laut Regency, then continued with coordination with the village head, village secretary, BPD chairman, and UMKM chairman. Next, implement communication assistance on marketing methods for UMKM products. The stages and methods of implementing activities are presented in the following table:

Table 1. Methods of Implementing Activities

Implementation stages	Activity	Method	Material
Observation	Carrying out observations in Lampa Village, Banggai District, Banggai Laut Regency	Direct interviews with local residents	Observations regarding the existence of local MSME products
Coordination	Coordinate with the head of Lampa village together with the village secretary,	Meeting with the village head, village secretary,	- Coordinate with the village head regarding time and place - Coordinate with the

	chairman of the BPD and heads of other MSMEs regarding the time and place for coordinating the implementation of mentoring activities that will be carried out in Lampa village.	BPD chairman and MSME chairman	secretary regarding time and place - Coordinate with the BPD chairman regarding the availability of local MSME products - Coordinate with the head of MSMEs regarding local MSME products as well as time and place
Implementation	Carrying out marketing communication strategy assistance for MSME products	Meeting with the head of MSMEs	Paccompanying marketing communications strategy in arousing consumer interest or interest in MSME products

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of individual work program activities with the head of UMKM in Lampa Dusun 2 village, Banggai subdistrict, and Banggai Laut district regarding communication assistance on marketing methods for UMKM products through innovation strategies that are carried out regularly to meet market needs and demands, including the strategy of creating market needs with the hope that the market will look for the product. and not vice versa, and price policy strategies that are adapted to market conditions, as well as the ability to adapt and analyze the social and economic realities of consumers and, most importantly, determine whether the product can provide true value to customers.

Figure 1. Activity

Prior to implementation, coordination was carried out on preparations for the implementation of marketing communication strategy assistance with the Lampa village government, Banggai District, and Banggai Laut Regency.

Figure 2. Implementation of Marketing Communication Strategy Assistance

Furthermore, assistance is provided with marketing communication strategies for the Serumpun UMKM group in an effort to strengthen local products so that they are able to compete in the market through regular product innovation based on market needs as well as strategies for creating market demand and market expectations for the products offered by the Serumpun UMKM group. Marketing communication strategies are also carried out through price policies in accordance with market conditions and the ability of UMKM to adapt to the current socio-economic realities of consumers.

Based on the results of a study of community service as a consideration for the progress of Serumpun UMKM products in Banggai Laut Regency, an appropriate marketing communications approach includes two important things, including the application of analysis and the marketing communications mix. If these two things are done well, the management of UMKM products will be able to enter local and national markets. The marketing communication strategies implemented include the following:

a. Marketing communication strategy through applied innovation

Innovation must be carried out intensively according to market demand and needs. This must be in accordance with human resource capabilities and the availability of raw materials so that it does not deviate from the regional characteristics and local wisdom where MSMEs develop. Innovation can also come from combining old designs with new designs to create the latest trends or fashions to meet market demand. Adapting to market changes, including changes in demand, is the key to UMK survival. This can be achieved by creating new products that meet society's current needs. UMKM players must have the ability to develop marketing communications strategies as part of change and adaptation to current circumstances. Currently, the most appropriate marketing communication strategies are digital, non-digital, and soft selling.

Innovations carried out by UMKM include not only products but also packaging. UMKM can try to use environmentally friendly packaging, such as environmentally friendly paper, or not use streofoam, cans, or plastic because the national market greatly reduces waste. In terms of marketing strategy, innovation can also be carried out. Using the digital world has many advantages, such as making a broad market easier and faster to reach and

giving customers the ability to interact directly with producers without being limited by distance, place, or time.

b. Marketing communication strategy through need creation

Banggai Laut Regency's allied UMKM products must have the ability to create needs, meaning that UMKM players are not only sensitive to market needs but also have the ability for the market to like, use, and use products created in a market that previously did not exist. So, the communication strategy must be able to create market needs. Basically, the marketing communications process is a communication process where the source conveys a message to the recipient through certain media. As (Ball, Coelho and Machás, 2004), mentions that "good communication should affect all aspects of a relationship, but most include trust, satisfaction, and loyalty".

In other words, the market is open to accepting innovations carried out by UMKM to meet its needs. This applies to the latest innovations that may not be known to the market or society. To maintain the existence of MSMEs in the market, needs must be met.

c. Marketing communication strategy through product pricing policies

The price policy strategy is one of the communication strategies where price setting is a weakness of UMKM in Banggai Laut, their superior products are sold at low prices but have competitive quality in the local and national markets. Therefore, a pricing policy strategy must be implemented. As stated (Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller, 2009) that the basic framework of marketing communications can be used to influence buyers regarding product style, price and shape, color and shape of packaging, business attitude and style, and store decoration.

One of these policy strategies that can be used is determining fair prices, which can be calculated through market research, where prices are set based on consumer capabilities. This means that if customers are from the upper class, they will receive products that are of higher quality and price, but if they are from the lower class, they will receive products of lower quality. By applying this method, it is believed that the products of small and medium enterprises (UMKM) in Banggai Laut Regency have the ability to meet market needs according to their market segmentation.

d. Marketing communication strategy through consumer social and economic adaptation

Serumpun UMKM products in Banggai Laut Regency must follow developments over time and market tastes so that the products can be adapted to consumer needs. MSME players must always be sensitive to changes and developing market tastes, both in local and national markets. Consumer needs are a mismatch between reality and internal drives (Mangkunegara, 2015). Manufacturers must not only consider financial capabilities and consumer preferences but also market realities. What the market wants is high-quality products without considering price, which is different from the local market, which prefers to get high-quality products at affordable prices.

To overcome this problem, it must be carefully considered. Manufacturers must have a marketing communication strategy through social adaptation in the national market by making premium-class products with

high-quality materials, professional labor, and safe packaging for customers without fear of offering high prices. The national market does not mind the price as long as the manufacturer is truly selling a premium-class product.

e. Marketing communication strategy through product value to consumers

UMKM producers in Bangang Laut must sell original goods that can be categorized according to market segment, from middle class to premium quality or cheap goods. One of the marketing strategies that must be implemented according to (Swastha, 2008) Communication is the key to developing UMKM promotional activities in the marketing sector. Communication is very important. All parts of the marketing mix include marketing communications, which assist exchanges by conveying meaning to customers or clients. (Shimp, 2000). According to marketing literature, building and maintaining profitable long-term relationships and increasing customer loyalty are the main goals of marketing activities.

Providing customized products is to reduce market disappointment with the product being made. If the product is provided with true value, consumers and the market will be able to receive a positive response. Positive responses and satisfaction are the keys to the success of marketing communication strategies and can determine the reputation and image of Serumpun UMKM products on the market. According to the results of the Daitas study, Serumpun UMKM producers are expected to be able to implement a number of communication strategies to strengthen the market so that they can penetrate the national market. Marketing communications carried out by UMKM will increase economic growth, employees, society, and local revenue.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Banggai Laut Regency has a lot of UMKM potential. This can provide opportunities for UMKM businesses to develop, but on the contrary, UMKMs superior products do not receive enough attention, so business declines as a result of product marketing challenges. One strategy that is rarely used to generate product sales is the right marketing communication strategy. UMKMs can learn and implement this strategy by continuously innovating to meet market demand, setting prices according to product quality, creating market needs, adapting and studying local market and economic capabilities, and knowing what consumers need.

FURTHER RESEARCH

Thank you, the chairman of the Luwuk Muhammadiyah University LP3M, the village head, the BPD chairman, and the chairman of the Lampa Village UMKMs, who have helped carry out service activities regarding marketing communication strategies for strengthening local MSME products. It is hoped that the results of this activity will allow UMKM players to be able to sell their products through product quality innovation that can compete in local and national markets.

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